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Influence of Psycho-Demographic Variables on Academic Resilience among Secondary School Students in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstracts

Resilience in an academic context is known as academic resilience. Academic resilience is a term that refers to a student's capacity to overcome difficulties that are considered severe or chronic in the educational process being undertaken. The study investigates influence of psycho-demographic variables on academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo State Nigeria. The population of the study consists of all government senior secondary school class two (SS2) students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Ibadan, Oyo State. 350 (200 male and 150 female) students were selected from the population using multi-stage sampling technique. Questionnaire titled IPVARASSS was content and face validated by experts in the field of psychology and analysed with a high reliability index of a .91. The generated five null hypotheses were tested using inferential statistics at 0.05 level of significant. The findings of the showed that level of academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan is high ($\bar{x} = 4.01 > 3.00$), there was significant difference in Academic resilience based on gender (male and female) among secondary school students in Ibadan ($T_{(348)} = .352, p < .05$), interest in schooling ($r(348) = .424p < .05$), learning orientation ($r(348) = .415p < .05$) and psychological flexibility ($r(348) = .502, p < .05$) had relationship to academic resilience among secondary school students. Based on findings of the study, the researcher concluded that psycho-demographic variables such as gender, interest in schooling, learning orientation and psychological flexibility are potential predictors of influences on academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. The researcher therefore, recommends among others that teacher and parents should assist students to find ways and means of enhancing their resilience in education and provision of adequate resources for teaching and learning that is capable of giving hope to students should be a requirement.

Keyword: Academic resilience, Interest in Schooling, Learning Orientation, Psycho-demographic, Psychological flexibility

Introduction

Resilience is the ability to maintain psychological stability in dealing with stress (Keye and Pidgeon, 2022). Resilience is one of the characteristics that enable academic achievement and also what distinguishes individuals who succeed from those who do not. Grotberg, (2017) explains that resilience is a combination of three sources (acceptance, purpose and flexibility), one of which is I am, which is a source that comes from within a person, resilience can be increased if someone has a power that comes from within themselves. In the academic context, resilience is characterized by students who have the ability to reverse academic failures and achieve success even though other things are performing poorly and failing, where this ability is called academic resilience (Cassidy, (2016)

Academic resilience has the ability to successfully cope with changes or adversity in academic situations; and dynamic processes of overcoming the negative effect of risk experiences with positive outcomes, avoiding negative trajectories associated with such risk. The literature on resilience among children and students shows that resilience tends to be dichotomized (Aldridge, Fraser, Fozdar, Ala'i, Earnest, and Afari, (2016) into individual focused characteristics and protective factors. In general, individually focused characteristics are identified through strategies directed towards modifying internal goals, problem solving strategies, and feelings of self-worth. Protective factors, on the other hand, focus on coping, and are reflected in strategies directed towards regulating or modifying external resources or support. Research has provided evidence for the significant role of resilience, when it is conceptualized as successful adaptation despite risk. For example, resilience has

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been used to characterise individuals who overcome difficult and challenging life circumstances and risk factors (Croson, and Elder, 2018).

The development of children in schools is threatened by all sorts of adversities such as lack instructional materials, incompetent teachers, bad school environment and poor teaching facilities that bear life-altering consequences for school going students. In the face of threats to human development, an integrated and global science of academic resilience informed by evidence based research is very much needed to inform government and international policymakers and intervention matters that mitigate risks and build academic resilience in children. Generally, the dynamic process of school going students show adaptive functioning in the face of significant adversity (Martin and Marsh, 2016).

In other words, this academic resilience will lead to an inferential concept conditional upon two major criteria. Firstly, there ought to be exposure of “serious risk” and secondly, there must be evidence of “good adaptation” in school environment. Unfortunately, despite strong scholarly interest in the study of students’ resilience, there is still a general lack of integrative understanding on the processes leading to academic resilience in development. A student may have an excellent academic record yet be experiencing chronic adversities in their personal life which could cause a major impediment to their academic success. Or, a poor test result could be crushing to a student who has never received anything other than good results, and could thereby cause a major impediment to their academic resilience if they have never learned how to bounce back from what they may perceive as a major failure (Agasisti and Longobardi, 2017). A common academic experience such as receiving a poor grade in a test or a piece of homework could require academic resilience if it constitutes an acute adversity for a particular student, given their circumstances, which could cause a major impediment to their academic success.

Interest of students in schooling occurs when "students make a psychological investment in learning. They try hard to learn what school offers. They take pride not simply in earning the formal indicators of success (grades), but in understanding the material and incorporating or internalizing it in their lives (Shapiro, Dundar, Wakhungu, Yuan, & Harrell, 2015). Students are engaged when they are involved in their work, persist despite challenges and obstacles, and take visible delight in accomplishing their work. Interest of students in schooling also refers to a "student's willingness, need, desire and compulsion to participate in, and be successful in, the learning process promoting higher level thinking for enduring understanding that leads to academic resilience (Taylor and Parsons, (2020)" Interest of students in schooling is also a usefully ambiguous term for the complexity of 'interest' in school and it is beyond the fragmented domains of cognition, behaviour, emotion or affect, and in doing so encompass the historically situated individual within their contextual variables (such as academic performance and resilience) that at every moment influence how engaged an individual (or group) is in their learning.

Interest of students in schooling is frequently used to, "depict students' willingness to participate in routine school activities, such as attending class, submitting required work, and following teachers' directions in class (Balwant, 2017)." However, the term is also increasingly used to describe meaningful student involvement throughout the learning environment, including students participating in curriculum design, classroom management and school building climate. It is also often used to refer as much to student involvement in extra-curricular activities in the campus life of a school/college/university which are thought to have educational benefits as it is to student focus on their curricular studies and enhance their academic resilience.

In a number of studies interest of students in schooling has been identified as a desirable trait in schools; however, there is little consensus among students and educators as to how to define it (Taylor, & Parsons, 2020). Interest of students in schooling is used to discuss students' attitudes towards school, while student disinterest identifies withdrawing from school in any significant way. The construct of student interest and its accompanying theories can better explain the linkage between communication and learning. Student academic resilience can be fostered by school factors such as immediacy and clarity and stimulated by student interest (Kahu, 2018).

Over the years, gender differences in academic resilience may explain the aforementioned differences in academic achievement. Gender plays an important role in resilience. Examining the gender perspective in academic resilience provides an insight regarding how male and female students conceptualize and express academic resilience in order to overcome setbacks. According to Morales (2008) gender has been identified as a crucial aspect of resilience yet gender differences in the resilience process have not been the focus of resilience studies. The combined effect of social background and gender is not analyzed frequently. Women and resilient students, who use education as a channel of mobility, are similar in that they tend to follow the manifest regulations of the education system.

This is demonstrated by their effort towards better grades and maximizing class attendance (Ceglédi 2018; Fényes 2010b; Fényes and Ceglédi 2015). The strategy seems effective in public education: females graduate from secondary education

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with better results and enter higher education in larger proportions, while resilient students, a subset of those who face social disadvantages, can also be regarded successful. After higher education, however, inequalities arise again: the literature shows the glass ceiling phenomenon for both women and disadvantaged students compared to less disadvantaged and male students, which may materialize in earnings or in the obtained positions (Laurison and Friedman 2019).

This category of orientation is characterized by students who are primarily interested in studying a particular subject 'for its own sake'. They are intellectually interested in the subject and are interested in studying at a higher level. Most students with this orientation already had some experience of the subject before coming to school and so tended to enhance their academic resilience (Bentley, 2022). They want to follow up aspects of the subject beyond the defined syllabus. Four distinct types of orientation and these were academic orientation, where the student's goals involved the academic side of school life; vocational orientation, where the student's goal was to get a job after school; personal orientation, where the student's goals were concerned with their personal development; and social orientation where the student's goals focused on the social side.

The first three of these orientations could be divided into two sub- types according to whether the student was directly interested in the content of the course or whether they were studying the course more as a means to an end. These sub-types distinguished in each case between intrinsic and extrinsic interest in the resilience of students in their academics. Agasisti and Longobardi, (2017) found that the concerns that students had while studying at school were intimately connected to the type of orientation they had, and that these orientations and their concerns helped to make sense of the amount of effort the student put into different aspects of their academic resilience.

Psychological flexibility affects individual problems. Kashdan and Rottenberg (2017), state that psychological flexibility has actually been known for more than 50 decades, but has different names such as resilience and self-regulation. Literature shows there are similarities and differences in the conceptualization of constructs, there are similarities in behavior changes (actions or thoughts) in response to changes in the environment. Whereas the difference in cognitive flexibility involves adjusting to changes in cues in the environment, while psychological flexibility does not only involve adjusting more aspects. According to Hayes in Bloombury (2022), psychological flexibility is defined as a person's ability to change or persist in conditions of behavior that benefit personal values. Rutter (2020), describes psychological flexibility as an individual's ability to adapt to stressful or adverse events. Kashdan and Rotterburg (2022) defining psychological flexibility as a measure of how a person: (1) adapts to the demands of the situation, (2) reconfigures mental resources, (3) shifts perspective, and (4) balances desires, needs, and domains life.

Psychological flexibility is more recent than cognitive flexibility and psychological flexibility studies can be done in clinical and non-clinical conditions while cognitive flexibility focuses on neuropsychology which is a clinical part (Whiting et al, 2015). There are several studies related to psychological flexibility, findings conducted by Foote et al (2016) show that someone who has psychological flexibility can reduce academic failure and increase academic resilience. Psychological flexibility can help a person have prosocial behavior which can help to improve their academics. Psychological flexibility is also closely related to self-efficacy, optimism and hope. The study of Montiel (2016) explains that psychological flexibility can prevent increased psychological distress such as anxiety and depression.

All this studies has been done to address the possible reasons behind the high failure rate and school dropout, however there still appears to be an increase in the rate of this worrisome dropout. Could psycho-demographic factors which has to do mainly on students' personal factor be the reason behind this lack of commitment and engagement to academic resilience? Therefore, the study tends to examines influence of psycho-demographic variables on academic resilience among students in Ibadan, Oyo, Nigeria.

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Objective of the study

1. The objective of the study is to investigate influence of psycho-demographic variables on academic resilience of Secondary School Students in Ibadan Nigeria.

Research Questions

One research questions was formulated to guide the conduct of this study:

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1. What is the level of academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo Nigeria?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between academic resilience among secondary school male and female students in Ibadan, Oyo State.
2. There is no significant relationship between level of interest and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo State.
3. There is no significant relationship between learning orientation and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo State.
4. There is no significant relationship between Psychological flexibility and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo State.

Methodology

This study used the descriptive survey design. The descriptive survey design was selected because it is appropriate for this study and there was not manipulation. The target population for this study consists of all secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state. The population of the study consists of all government senior secondary school class two (SS2) students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Ibadan, Oyo State. 350 (200 male and 150 female) students were selected from the population using multi-stage sampling technique. This is in three stages; the first stage randomly selections of 3 local government (Ibadan North, Ido and Akinyele) from the 11 local government areas that make up Ibadan, which lead to the stage two, six (6) schools (two schools from each local government) were selected through simple random sampling techniques from the earlier selected local government, and at stage three, purposely sampling techniques was adopted in selecting participant (in secondary school students) students from the sample schools.

After face and content validation of the instrument by experts in the area of psychology, Questionnaire titled IPVARASSS was appropriately administered to the selected respondents and collated for analysis.

. The data collected was analyzed through the use of frequency distribution, hypothesis 1 was analysed using T-test while hypothesis 2, 3 and 4, respectively were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

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Hypothesis one: There is no significant difference between academic resilience among secondary school male and female students in Ibadan, Oyo State.

Table 2: Summary Table of t-test for independent measures showing comparison of Academic resilience based on gender

	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	T	Sig
Academic resilience	Male	136	100.79	10.95			
					348	.352	.549

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Female	214	99.92	11.19
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From Table 2, the result showed that there was significant difference in Academic resilience based on gender (male and female) among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state ($T_{(348)} = .352, p < .05$). From the table above, a mean score of 100.79 for male participants while female participants had a mean score of 99.92 with a mean difference of 0.87 and statistically significant.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between level of interest and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo State.

Table 3 showing PPMC summary on the relationship between interest in schooling and academic resilience

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	R	Sig	P
Interest in schooling	350	97.89	13.35	348	.424	.000	<0.05
Academic resilience		100.26	11.09				

Table 3 show the significant relationship between interest in schooling and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state. The result revealed that there is significant relationship between interest in schooling and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state; $r_{(348)} = .424p < .05$. This implies that interest in schooling had moderate influence on academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state.

Hypothesis three: There is no significant relationship between learning orientation and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo State.

Table 4 showing PPMC summary on the relationship between learning orientation and academic resilience of students

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	R	Sig	P
Learning orientation	350	38.02	5.67	348	.415	.000	<0.05
Academic resilience		100.26	11.09				

Table 4 show the significant relationship between learning orientation and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state. The result revealed that there is significant relationship between learning orientation and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state; $r_{(348)} = .415p < .05$. This implies that learning orientation had moderate influence on academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state.

Hypothesis Four: There is no significant relationship between Psychological flexibility and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo State.

Table 5 showing PPMC summary on the relationship between psychological flexibility and academic resilience

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	R	Sig	P
Psychological flexibility	350	45.11	7.01	348	.502	.000	<0.05
Academic resilience		100.26	11.09				

Table 5, showing the significant relationship between psychological flexibility and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state. The result revealed that there is significant relationship between psychological flexibility and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state; $r_{(348)} = .502, p < .05$. This implies that psychological flexibility had strong influence on academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state.

Discussion of Findings

Table 1 research question 1 is in line with the study of Brookhart, & Durkin, (2013) found that self-selected texts increased the readers' positive feelings about reading and improved achievement scores. The study found that self-selection was important when attempting to motivate students to read and that non-fiction could be just as motivating as fiction (Moss & Hendershot, 2014). The importance of student interest was a key take away from that study, and this is an important factor for teachers to remember, although not just with middle school students. Hargrove's (2014), results of this teacher's study and determined that the student-directed assignment was successful, resulting in increased energy and output. The teacher-led assignment showed the same results that led to the teacher's initial frustration and motivation to begin the study in the first

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place. The teacher viewed students as individuals and took their interests and personalities into consideration when creating the assignment.

In table 2 hypotheses 1, the result indicated a significant relationship which is in support with the study of Scales et al in Jonson (2019), whose work showed that resilience has a high correlation with students' achievement index in America at various schools at the high school level. Various studies have also shown that the various resilience skills developed by students can have a significant effect on academic performance (Christine, 2010). Several studies related to academic resilience focus on specific ethnic groups or groups of students (Gizir & Aydin, 2009; Borman & Overman, 2021). However, research on academic resilience is relevant to all students, including students at the university. All students at all academic levels tend to experience various difficulties, challenges, pressures, or poor performance in the academic process (Martin & Marsh, 2020). Resilience should be a concern for universities considering this can be a factor in student survival in studying at higher education. On the other hand, this study contradicts a study by Khalaf (2014). The study shows that men and women have significant differences in the level of academic resilience. Research conducted by Sarwar et. al. (2010) in Pakistan also identified that men are more resilient than women. Research conducted by Morales (2020) also shows that there are significant differences between men and women in academic resilience where women are more resilient than men. Somchit and Sriyaporn (2010) also stated that women have higher resilience than male students.

Also, table 3 hypothesis 2 is in accordance with the study of Hardr, Sullivan, and Crowson (2012), that state that when students saw value and relevance in what they were learning and how it could help achieve their goals, they were more likely to have increased interest, put forth effort, and graduate going on to post-secondary opportunities (Hardr, Sullivan & Crowson). In addition, the more competent they felt about their abilities, the more likely they were to commit to continued study and education. Therefore, the interest these students felt in their learning had a significant impact on their feelings of success, and, ultimately, their performance. It is important that students view their learning experiences as authentic and meaningful. Marks (2010) purported that three factors influence student engagement and learning: personal background and orientation toward school, school initiatives, and subject matter. She looked at 24 schools undergoing restructuring, specifically grades 5, 8, and 10. Students completed surveys about their attitudes, behaviors, and experiences, their general school experience, and their personal/family background. She was able to draw several conclusions from her study. First, like Skinner et al., student engagement decreased as grade level increased; high school students reported the least positive orientation toward schools. By contrast, feelings of being supported in the classroom were highest among elementary school students. Subject matter did have an effect on reports of authentic work (that is, student feeling that the work is challenging and relevant). Successful students were more engaged, but students who reported feeling alienated were less to (Marks).

Furthermore, the result of table 4 hypothesis 3 is in accordance to the work of Csikszentmihalyi, Schneider, and Shernoff (2023). Their study found that student engagement increases when students find the task challenging, balanced, relevant, and under their control. They determined this by asking 526 students to track their academic activities throughout the course of the school day and record how they felt during those activities. Students felt most engaged when participating in a group activity or discussion as opposed to listening to a lecture. They concluded that, based on Csikszentmihalyi's (1997) flow theory, concentration, interest, and enjoyment in an activity must all be present. All of the studies above support the argument that student interest plays a key role in student success. Interest is necessary for continuing motivation and learning. Like Hardr, Sullivan, and Crowson, Shernoff et al. found that challenge and satisfaction in task completion will motivate students and engage their interest.

Lastly, result of table 5 hypothesis 4 is in line with the study of Zepke and Leach (2010), which states that when students have some semblance of control over their learning, they are more likely to be engaged and achieve academic success. Tella, Adeniyi and Olufemi (2018) support this claim with the conclusions of their study. They found that locus of control, interest in schooling, and self-efficacy are all factors in predicting academic achievement. Locus of control refers to an individual's belief of what causes success. It can be internal, where the student believes success is due to personal effort and ability and is more likely to work hard. Students who believe in an external locus of control will attribute their success to luck or fate, and may not put forth as much effort. More significant to this review are the results that analyzed student interest in schooling. Several studies have shown that differences in resilience between men and women are also influenced by biological factors (Rinaldi, 2010), socio-demographic factors (Wardhani et al., 2017), and socio-emotional factors (Sunarti et al., 2018). Generally, women tend to use emotion-focused coping more often in dealing with pressure when having problems, namely by placing more emphasis on overcoming emotional impacts that arise (Brougham et al., 2018). Physical differences also have an impact on the resilience of men and women. Women are considered more difficult to manage and access resources that can

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help them solve the problems they face, so they are more easily swayed than men (Kumar & Quisumbing, 2014). If analyzed more simply, it can be concluded that resilience is formed and influenced by at least three things, namely: personality factors, biological factors, and environmental factors (Herrman, 2016).

Conclusion

The weighted mean is greater than the standard mean. This implies that the level of academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan is high. There was significant difference in Academic resilience based on gender (male and female) among secondary school students in Ibadan. Also, interest in schooling had significant relationship to academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan. There is significant relationship between learning orientation and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan. The study also revealed that there was significant difference in Academic resilience based on gender (male and female) among secondary school students in Ibadan, there is significant relationship between interest in schooling and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan. More so, there is significant relationship between learning orientation and academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan, the result indicates that there was a significant contribution of of interest in schooling, psychological flexibility and learning orientation to academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan and lastly, factors such as interest in schooling and learning orientation predict and determine academic resilience among secondary school students in Ibadan.

Recommendations

Based on the results of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The teachers and parents should help students to find ways and means of enhancing their resilience in school
2. Provision of adequate resource for teaching and learning should be a requirement.
3. Enough time should be given to the implementation of new innovations.
4. Full parent participation in the welfare of their children should be seriously considered in schools (strengthening the PTA).
5. The school leadership should play a leading role when it comes to students' performance and resilience since it is believed that a school is as good as its head.
6. Findings of the present study may help to improve academic resilience of students as they are a wakeup call to students, teachers, school managers and parents among many education stake holders.

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